

4-Thiazolidinones

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Manuscript received 27 April 1974; revised 30 November 1974; accepted 2 May 1975

Some mixed 3-aryl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidinones have been synthesised by condensing N,N'-diaryl thioureas with monochloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in absolute ethanol. The fungicidal activity of these 4-Thiazolidinones has also been assayed.

A number of 4-thiazolidinones and their derivatives show a wide variety of physiological properties and biological activities^{1,2}.

In a view to study some potential biological activities, several mixed 4-thiazolidinones containing different aryl groups at positions 2 and 3 in the ring have been synthesised by the condensation of various N, N' diaryl thioureas with monochloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in ethanolic medium. A typical reaction is given below :

The structure of the various mixed 4-thiazolidinones prepared as above were proved by hydrolysing them with ethanolic hydrochloric acid into the corresponding 2,4-thiazolidinediones and comparing the latter with the authentic samples already described in the literature. Melting points, determined in open capillaries in sulphuric acid bath are uncorrected.

Experimental

Preparation of 3-o-methylphenyl-2-p-Nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone :

3-o-tolyl-1-nitrophenylthiourea (15 g.), monochloroacetic acid (5 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (8 g.) and absolute ethanol (60 ml.) were refluxed together on a water bath for 5 hr. The excess of ethanol was distilled off and the reaction mixture was poured into cold water. The precipitate was filtered and washed several times with hot water to remove unreacted monochloroacetic acid and sodium acetate. It was dried and recrystallised from ethanol—as yellowish crystal (10.55 g; yield 62%), m.p. 115°. Analysis found : C, 58.442; H, 3.542; N, 12.528; S, 9.320. C₁₆H₁₃N₂O₃S requires C, 85.715; H, 3.975; N, 12.844; S, 9.786%.

Preparation of 3-o-Hydroxy phenyl-2-p-chlorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone :

Mixture of 3-o-Hydroxy phenyl-1-p-chlorophenyl thiourea (12 g.), monochloroacetic acid (4.5 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (6 g.) and absolute ethanol (50 ml.) was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hr. Worked up in the usual way and the precipitate obtained was collected, washed, and dried. It was purified by dissolving in dilute sodium hydroxide and reprecipitating with equivalent amount of dilute hydrochloric acid, filtered, washed with water and dried, m.p. 180° (8 g, yield 58.3%). Analysis found : C, 56.920; H, 3.262; N, 8.344; S, 10.442. C₁₅H₁₁N₂O₂SCl requires C, 56.514; H, 3.453; N, 8.791; S, 10.047%.

Analytical data and the physical properties of other mixed 4-thiazolidinones prepared by anyone of the above methods are given in Table 1.

Hydrolysis of 3-o-methylphenyl-2-p-nitrophenyl imino-4-thiazolidinone :

3-o-methylphenyl-2-p-nitrophenyl imino-4-thiazolidinone (2 g.), ethanol (20 ml.) and conc. hydrochloric acid (5 ml.) were refluxed on a water bath for 4 hr. Worked up in the usual way the precipitate was recrystallised from ethanol to give pure 3-o-methylphenyl-2,4-thiazolidinedione^{3,4}, m.p. 154° (1.5 g.).

Hydrolysis of 3-o-hydroxyphenyl-2-p-chlorophenylimino-4-thiazolidinone :

This 4-thiazolidinone was hydrolysed to 3-o-hydroxy phenyl-2,4-thiazolidinedione in the same way as described in the previous experiment. Compared the m.p. and other properties with that of authentic sample⁵ and found to be the same.

Hydrolysis products :

Compound No. 1 to 7 were hydrolysed as above and the 2,4-thiazolidinediones obtained were compared with authentic sample. Hydrolysis products are tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE 1

Compound No.	Ar	Ar ¹	Colour	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis			
							C	H	N	S
1.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Yellowish	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	115	62	Found 58.422 Calc. 58.715	3.542 3.975	12.528 12.844	9.320 9.786
2.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Yellowish	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	104	60	Found 58.383 Calc. 58.715	3.484 3.975	12.616 12.844	9.381 9.786
3.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Yellowish	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	158	65	Found 58.296 Calc. 58.715	4.046 3.975	12.408 12.844	9.414 9.786
4.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	White	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ 5Cl	180	58.3	Found 56.920 Calc. 56.514	3.262 3.453	8.344 8.791	10.442 10.047
5.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	White	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ IS	160	60	Found 44.082 Calc. 43.902	2.924 2.683	6.601 6.829	7.280 7.805
6.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	Yellowish	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ IS	80	78	Found 41.422 Calc. 41.002	2.504 2.279	9.980 9.567	7.642 7.289
7.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	Yellowish	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₃ IS	102	80	Found 41.386 Calc. 41.002	2.446 2.279	9.708 9.567	7.526 7.289

Fungicidal Activity

The fungicidal activity of these 4-thiazolidinones was assayed by the method of Horsfall⁸. *Alternaria solani* was used as a representative test fungus.

The fungicidal activity of all the given compounds (cpd. No. 1-7 in Table 1) prepared during this work has been evaluated. All the compounds screened, showed the considerable activity, out of which compound No. 4 (Table 1) was found to be most active.

TABLE 2

Compound No.	Ar	Colour	m.p. °C	Reference No.
1	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	White	154	3, 4
2	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	White	90	6
3	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	White	162	7
4	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	White	191	5
5	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	White	>300	5
6	<i>m</i> -Nitro	Yellow	76	5
7	<i>p</i> -Nitro	Yellow	147	7

The percentage inhibition was calculated as follows :

$$\text{Percentage inhibition} = \frac{(X - Y)}{X} \times 100.$$

where X = area of the colony in control plate
 Y = area of the colony in test plate.

Acknowledgements

The author is thankful to his colleagues for the help and encouragement.

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